

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL AND STYLISTIC ASPECTS IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *This article aims to deal with the topic the role of cultural and stylistic aspects in literary translation. The article focuses on valuable information about the importance of culture in translating process, its function and difficulties. Moreover, facts about peculiarities of stylistics in literary translation were noted by author.*

Key words: *literary translation, culture-specific concepts, compromise, source text's style, nonliterary texts, cognitive dimensions, tentative, stylistic features.*

According to Umberto Eco (2001: 17), "Translation is always a shift, not between two languages, but between two cultures". This phenomenon is especially prominent in literary translation, since it heavily depends on the culture of the source text (ST) and it is inextricably intertwined with its aesthetic quality. Given that a language is intricately attached to its corresponding culture, translating various culture-specific concepts into another culture can be quite challenging. Although translation theory examines these phenomena and provides numerous classifications of translation strategies that might help the translator in coping with the problems of translating culturally specific elements, the final solution is often a compromise and depends on a set of choices that a translator has to make. In other words, each translation of a culture-specific item (CSI) is a particular translational situation which depends on various criteria.

A good literary translation must reproduce something of the source text's style; otherwise the distinguishing literariness in the original will not be conveyed in the target text. Special techniques, craft, and rhetorical effects are characteristics of literary texts compared with nonliterary texts, and hence they should be captured and properly maintained; the maintenance is pertinent to the translator's awareness of them (most importantly), the linguistic and cultural restrictions, and the target audiences. Generally, the rule of thumb can be: the literal translation of the wording related to the techniques is the basic requirement if there is no

linguistic or cultural gap, but where a gap exists, a re-creation that is different from literal translation may be called for to render the same poetic effect. Occasionally, something that is footnoted even for native English-using readers, being beyond the assumed shared knowledge of ordinary readers, might need to be footnoted for the target text readers too. Knowledge of stylistic approaches to translation can help us understand more about what style is, what its effects are, how it works and how it becomes transformed in the translation process ... knowledge of theory might also allow us to read for translating more effectively, by paying close attention to style and recognizing what is important for its effects, by being open to its cognitive dimensions, and by enjoying an enhanced awareness of what is universal and what is culturespecific[2]. Such knowledge can inform decisions made during translation, however tentative they are. Style is not merely a sense; it is something embedded in the language of a literary text. Stylistics supplies systematic and coherent theoretical linguistic approaches to investigate the style, rather than taking it for granted as intuition. For literary translators, stylistics can help identify important stylistic features in the source text, and can help us to evaluate whether equivalent features are or are not present in one or several translations of that original and whether the equivalent functions are or are not achieved.

It is also worthwhile to note that sometimes stylistic features are functional in subtle ways yet they are not necessarily noticed by the reader or listener, and here stylistics attempts to develop the fundamental concerns of these features and functions that go “beyond the hunches of the Common Reader”. Stylistics can identify the dominant feature(s) of a linguistic phenomenon, which might be the privileged concern for a translator’s translation strategy. For instance, stylisticians believe that the cognitive process of metaphorical utterances is essential, namely, how to communicate rather than what to communicate should be the focus. Built on this theoretical concern, the creative translation strategy, which attempts to produce a similar cognitive process, is allowed for and called for. In other words, the re-creation in translation gains its solid position in literary translation thanks to stylistics.

Translation of elements and concepts embedded in a specific culture occupies a special place in translation theory. We should note that different authors refer to these elements by using different terms and definitions. For instance, Ivir and Newmark use the term “cultural word”, Florin uses “realia”, Mailhac and Olk use “cultural reference”, Franco Aixelá and Kwieciński use “culture-specific item” and Pedersen uses

“extralinguistic cultural reference” (Pavlović 2015: 70). According to Veselica Majhut, the definitions of all these terms have two features in common: the elements are culturally specific, insofar as they witness gaps or non-correspondences between the source language (SL) and the target language (TL), and as such they are identified as a translation problem.

The process of translating (interpreting) described as a two-stage process follows the scheme introduced by A. Shveitser [5] and O. Cherednichenko [3] which accounts for linguistic and extralinguistic factors, the most important of which is culture both source and target ones. According to this pattern translating is a two-stage process of interlingual and cross-cultural communication, during which an interpreter, on the basis of an analysed and transformed text in the source language, creates another text in the target language, which substitutes the source text in the target language and culture [1, p. 30]. In the process of translating (interpreting) besides phonological, lexical and grammatical aspects of successful interpretation communicative one is the most relevant as the interpreter should bear in mind specific cultural background and extralinguistic factors of both the source and target languages. Translation patterns construct a domestic representation and fix stereotypes for foreign cultures, signifying respect for cultural difference and participating in the process of identity formation and geopolitical relations establishing. The issue of a translation ethics on the relationship between two cultures arises here as translation, being open to target language cultural values, can be powerful in the hierarchy of moral norms maintaining and promoting in both source- and target-language groups cultures through choosing translation strategy. There is a plethora of translation strategies among which is the Domestication strategy, also called normalization or naturalization strategy, employed to bridge cultural gaps and achieve intelligibility in line with the hermeneutic approach which focuses on interpretation and grants the translator the right to manipulate the text so as to make it natural, comprehensible and readable, an approach in which the original text undergoes adaptation so as to be re-created to comply with the target linguistic and cultural conventions and to fulfill the function or purpose of translation, i.e. *skopos* [6, p. 60–75].

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